

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 2

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 2** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

The wildfires that ravaged Greece during the 2021 fire season were unparalleled in their intensity, extent, and destructive impact. As per the European Forest Fire Information System data, Greece experienced a staggering total of 79 events, each spanning more than 30 hectares, scorching approximately 130,000 hectares in total. These numbers represent the most severe recorded devastation in the country since 2009. Notably, Greece ranked second-worst among the 27 EU member countries in terms of the total burnt area, with Italy topping the list (160,000 ha). Further, Greece displayed the most alarming performance regarding the average burnt area per event, with 1,650 hectares per event.

The recent Greek wildfires align with the broader trend of evolving fire landscapes due to climate change, a trend emphasized in the latest report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. This new wildfire reality presents elongated fire seasons with more frequent occurrences of extreme events. Confronting this challenge necessitates a crucial investment in scientific knowledge to bolster preparedness.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
17.12.2021

HIGHWAY TO THE HELL OF AUGUST

The **August 2021 inferno** in Greece was not that surprising. In contrast, it was the natural outcome of a series of events that contributed to building up a **very high potential** for the occurrence of extreme wildfires. This potential was not generated in a couple of days, but it has been building up since the very **beginning of the fire season**.

The occurrence of large and often catastrophic wildfires is a complex phenomenon controlled by **4 environmental “switches”** (see image on the left). First, fuels need to be abundant enough to sustain fire spread (**Switch 1**). Second, fuels need to be dry enough to allow for the ignition of fire and sustain combustion (**Switch 2**). With fuels available and dry enough, any source of heat (e.g., lightning, arson) can result in the ignition of a wildfire (**Switch 3**). Depending on fire weather, any ignited wildfire can escalate in terms of size and intensity, eventually evolving into an extreme event (**Switch 4**).

The availability of **spatially continuous and dry fuels** is a prerequisite for the occurrence of extreme wildfires (Switches 1 and 2). This required ingredient was present in the August 2021 Greek wildfires. This is concluded from the examination of the **dead fuel moisture content time series**, derived from the measurements of the automatic weather stations (AWSs) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). For instance, the dead fuel moisture content estimated at the AWS in Tatoi was relatively low (below 15 %) since the end of May, while it declined further by the end of June to values lower than 10 % (see image below). These data indicate that the area affected by the Varympompi wildfire was in a **critically flammable condition** since the end of June, while during the ignition and spread of the fire, the dead fuel moisture content was extremely low, ranging between 6 – 7 %. Similar conclusions were drawn by examining the time series of the dead fuel moisture content for the wildfires that broke out in Euboea, Elis, Laconia, and Messenia.

As fuels were abundant (also due to the Medea snowstorm that impacted fire-affected regions in February 2021) and extremely dry, it is of interest to look at the evolution of **fire weather conditions** through the **ISI** (Initial Spread Index, rating for the expected rate of spread) and **FWI** (Fire Weather Index, rating for the expected fire intensity) components of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System (CFFWIS). As shown in the following image, the ignition of the Varympompi wildfire coincided with the absolute maxima (since the beginning of the fire season) of both ISI and FWI. This implies that fire weather conditions were **highly conducive** to the rapid spread of intense-burning wildfires. Further, it is worth noting that the deterioration of fire weather began in late June. Similar conclusions were also drawn by examining the corresponding data for the wildfires that spread across Euboea, Elis, Laconia, and Messenia.

In conclusion, **the extreme wildfires of August 2021 should have not caught the Greek state by surprise**. On the contrary, there were robust indications, since the end of June, that the country was heading towards a period with extremely high potential for the occurrence of extreme

wildfires. This highlights the urgent need for better monitoring of the environmental conditions that have the potential to lead to extreme wildfires to provide timely and science-based early warnings.

MEDEA AND TWO HEATWAVES: AN EXPLOSIVE RELATIONSHIP

During the period 13 – 17 February 2021, Greece was affected by an intense and persistent cold intrusion (see image above). The anticipated extremely low temperatures and the intense weather phenomena forced the Meteo Unit of the National Observatory of Athens to name the expected storm, **MEDEA**.

During the MEDEA storm, Greece was influenced by **heavy rainfall and snowfall**. In particular, the south and eastern mainland regions experienced very heavy snowfalls that resulted in **significant snow accumulations** on the ground. As a result, pine forests were heavily impacted. Broken branches and logs contributed to the **build-up of fuels** at the surface. This is primarily attributed to the nature of the MEDEA snowfalls.

Different types of snow are characterized by different weights. The more the water contained in snow, the heavier the snow is. Dry snow occurs under very low temperatures and is the lighter of all snows. Regular snow occurs under slightly low temperatures and is approximately three times heavier than dry snow. Wet snow occurs when surface temperatures are around 0 °C and is the heaviest one since it contains a lot of water; it weighs about seven times the weight of dry snow. Therefore, the impact of the same volume of snow varies depending on whether the snow is dry or wet. During MEDEA, temperatures were only slightly negative. As a result, **a lot of water was present in the falling snow**. In turn, this resulted in large accumulations of wet, **heavy snow** that caused severe damages in the pine forests of the south and eastern Greek mainland.

Following the adverse impacts of MEDEA on the pine forests of south and eastern Greece, the summer of 2021 was marked by **significant positive temperature anomalies**, which locally exceeded 2 °C (reference period: 1981 – 2010). Significant contributors to these positive departures from the climatic mean were **two intense heatwaves** that affected Greece; one in late June and one in late July. The main characteristic of both heatwaves was the persistence of high temperatures (> 40 °C) and low humidity (10 – 20 %) for a long period (> 10 days). It is worth noting that the summer of 2021 in Greece was marked as one with the most “warm hours” during the last 43 years.

The two intense heatwaves, combined with the generally high springtime and summertime temperatures, the lack of precipitation, and the atmospheric moisture deficit contributed significantly to the effective drying of fuels that accumulated owing to MEDEA. The combination of these events was a key factor in increasing the availability of dry enough fuels, ultimately generating an environment conducive to extreme wildfires.

THE PYROCONVECTION OUTBREAK

The catastrophic Greek wildfires of August 2021 were characterized by **extreme fire behavior**, showing erratic fire spread, prolific spotting, and the **formation of pyroclouds** (see image on the left).

Pyroconvection is a common behavioral feature of large and often extreme wildfires. The formation of pyroclouds is as much an atmospheric phenomenon as a process related to the fire itself. The intense heat released by a fire warms the air and forces it to begin rising. As the warm air rises, cooler air begins flowing toward the fire, ultimately creating a feedback loop that tends to enhance the intensity of burning. At higher altitudes, the rising warm air begins to cool and expand as a result of the decreasing atmospheric pressure. As soon as it is cooled enough, water vapor present in the rising plume begins condensing on ash particles, eventually leading to the formation of a cumuliform cloud just above the smoke plume. This cloud is called a **pyrocumululus** and if the intensity of a burning fire is sufficiently large, it can continue developing into a pyrocumulonimbus, as happened in the case of the Varympompi wildfire (see image on the right). These clouds are similar in structure to storm clouds and may significantly jeopardize the safety of firefighting crews since they are associated with strong and gusty winds and dense spotting over long distances.

It is worth noting at this point that not all wildfires have the potential to create pyroclouds. In particular, the formation of pyroclouds requires **three ingredients**, all linked to the **vertical structure of the atmosphere**. First, the near-surface conditions need to be warm and dry enough to sustain the intense burning of fuels. Second, the lowest layer of the troposphere, just above the fire, needs to be relatively deep, dry, and unstable, with minimum wind shear. Third, the upper layer of the troposphere, where condensation takes place, needs to be sufficiently moist to support and enhance the buoyancy of the rising smoke plume.

The occurrence of pyroconvection indicates clearly that **a wildfire is generating its own weather**. The local-scale atmospheric circulation associated with pyroconvective wildfires is characterized by often violent updrafts and downdrafts, significant intensification of surface winds, and prolific spotting over long distances. As the formation of pyroclouds is directly linked to atmospheric stability (which, in turn, is subject to a diurnal cycle), the collapse of these clouds can result in erratic fire spread through the ignition of new spot fires and the intensification of the surface winds that drive the movement of the fire fronts (see image on the left).

VARYMPOMPI 2021: ABSENCE OF STRONG WINDS

A **common public perception** in Greece is that strong winds need to be blowing for a wildfire to escalate. While partially true, this perception is fundamentally misleading. This was proven during the recent catastrophic wildfires of August 2021, when the major subject of public discussion was **“Why did the wildfires escalate without strong winds?”**.

Indeed, the wind is a factor with a large and direct impact on the behavior and spread of a wildfire. It is the wind that supplies fire with the necessary oxygen, also guiding the movement of the fire fronts. However, **a wildfire can evolve into an extreme event even in the absence of significant wind**. When the wind is not that strong, it is easier for a wildfire to develop its own circulation (make its own weather) and evolve into a **plume-driven event**, eventually exhibiting extreme fire behavior. Under these conditions, the key requirement is the sustaining of intense burning, which can be achieved when fuels are abundant and dry.

The recent Varympompi wildfire makes a characteristic example of an extreme event under generally light wind conditions. Owing to the abundant, extremely dry fuels, the Varympompi

wildfire developed into a plume-driven (made its own weather) event, showing extreme fire behavior and escalating rapidly in terms of its extent and intensity.

The **numerical simulations** that were conducted with the **IRIS 2.0** fire spread forecasting system operated at IERSD/NOA show particular interest. More specifically, we carried out two numerical experiments to knock down the common perception of the role of strong winds. In the first experiment, the Varympompi fire spread was simulated using the actual meteorological conditions of the day of ignition (light winds, high temperatures, low rel. humidity). In the second experiment, fire spread was simulated under a hypothetical scenario of strong north-easterly winds, which corresponds to a more typical summer situation in the study area. The results are shown in the image below.

A quick look at the fire spread maps is enough to demystify the role of strong winds. IRIS 2.0 results indicate that **strong winds would have not allowed for the Varympompi wildfire to escalate**. This is because the strong north-easterly winds would have driven the fire to the southwest, hindering its lateral expansion. However, the light winds that were blowing allowed the fire to quickly spread in all cardinal directions. Moving into an area rich in extremely dry fuels, particularly to the north, the fire sustained intense burning, developed a strong convective column, and eventually evolved into a plume-driven event with extreme fire behavior.

FLAME PUBLICITY FACTS

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

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Conference posters and presentations

Giannaros TM, Kotroni V, Lagouvardos K. IRIS – Operational implementation and evaluation during the 2019 fire season. Presentation at the 15th International Conference on Meteorology, Climatology, and Atmospheric Physics, 27 September 2021, Ioannina, Greece.

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G, Lagouvardos K, Kotroni V, Dafis S, Karagiannidis A (2021) Early warning of extreme pyroconvective events – Lessons learned from the early August 2021 wildfires in Greece. Presentation at the 8th International Conference on Civil Protection and New Technologies, 24 November 2021, Online. The recorded presentation (in Greek) can be found [here](#).

FLAME in the media

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7675163/fotia-sti-varybobi-o-rolos-pou-epaixe-to-kokteil-kafsona-ygrasias-kai-anemon-ti-lene-oi-pyrometeorologoi> (03.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7693329/foties-stin-ellada-oi-pyrkagies-terata-typou-kalifornias-kai-o-ellipis-kai-aparchaiomenos-tropos-antimetopisis-tous> (09.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7721677/fotia-sta-vilia-timelapse-vinteo-me-tin-exelixi-tis-pyrkagias> (18.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7720783/fotia-sta-vilia-exelissetai-se-aftokathodigoumeni-lene-oi-pyrometeorologoi> (18.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7723354/i-ekrxi-tis-fotias-sta-vilia-pou-apodidetai-i-akraia-syberifora-pyros> (19.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7731903/fotia-sta-vilia-exasthenisi-ton-anemon-arga-apogevma> (23.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7721426/fotia-sta-vilia-i-pyrkagia-emfanizei-akraia-syberifora-ti-lene-oi-pyrometeorologoi> (23.08.2021)

<https://www.newsbeast.gr/greece/arthro/7732281/fotia-sta-vilia-orati-apo-to-diastrima-i-nea-pyrkagia> (23.08.2021)

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